

Short communication

First record of the fruit fly *Urophora vera* (Dip.: Tephritidae) from Iran

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چکیده

مطالعه فونستیک گونه‌های جنس *Urophora* Robineau-Desvoidy (Diptera: Tephritidae) در دو استان آذربایجان شرقی و آذربایجان غربی در طول سال‌های ۱۳۹۲ و ۱۳۹۳ انجام شد. در این تحقیق گونه *Urophora vera* Kurneyev & White از روی گیاه (*Serratula* sp. (Asteraceae)) از تیره مرکبان جمع‌آوری و پرورش داده شد. این گونه برای اولین بار از ایران گزارش می‌شود.

The genus *Urophora* Robineau-Desvoidy 1830 with about 60 species is one of the largest genera of the family Tephritidae in the Palearctic region and is being placed in the subfamily Tephritinae and the tribe Myopitini (Norrbon *et al.*, 1999; Norrbom, 2004). The genus may be separated from other genera of Myopitini by the following combination of characters: Proboscis spatulate to short geniculate; labella length:head length ratio 0.3 to 0.8; labella length:head height ratio 0.2 to 0.7. Costal setulae small, not erect. Scutellum yellow medially, convex. Wing usually with distinct bands, sometimes reduced, rarely hyaline. Hosts: Cardueae. Predominantly live in Palearctic region (Freidberg & Norrbom, 1999).

reared from flower heads of *Serratula* sp., 2 females, 14.10.2013

Diagnosis. First flagellomere strongly pointed apicodorsally; Base of basal scutellar setae located on yellow area; femura yellow, without black strips; Wing hyaline with dark brown crossbands. Subbasal Crossband narrow, from R1 to A1; discal crossband complete, reaches posterior margin of the wing; preapical and apical crossbands fused in anterior margin of wing. Aculeus apex with only one pair of preapical steps (Fig. 1).

Distribution. Armania (Korneyev & White, 1996) and Iran (New record for Iran).

Host plant. *Serratula* sp. (Korneyev & White, 1996)

***Urophora vera* Korneyev and White, 1996**

Material examined: Province of East Azarbaijan, Ajabshir, 37°33' N, 45°50' E, 1540m,

Fig. 1. *Urophora vera*: (A) wing, head (lateral view) and pleura; (B) oviscape; (C) aculeus apex

References

- Freidberg, A. & Norrbom, A. L.** (1999) A generic reclassification and phylogeny of the tribe Myopitini (Tephritinae). pp. 581-627 in Aluja, M. & Norrbom, A. L. (Eds) *Fruit flies (Tephritidae): Phylogeny and Evolution of Behavior*. 987 pp. CRC Press.
- Korneyev, V. A. & White, I. M.** (1996) Fruit flies of the genus *Urophora* R.-D. (Diptera: Tephritidae) of Eastern Palaearctic. *Entomological Review* 76,499-513.
- Norrbom, A. L., Carroll, L. E., Thompson, F. C., White, I. M. & Freidberg, A.** (1999) Systematic database of names. pp. 65-251 in Thompson, F.C. (Ed) *Fruit fly expert identification system and systematic information database*. 524 pp. Diptera Data Dissemination Disk (CD-ROM).
- Norrbom, A. L.** (2004) Updates to biosystematic database of world diptera for Tephritidae through 1999. Diptera Data Dissemination Disk [CD-ROM].